

The World Around Us

Trying to describe the world is certainly no easy task, however, one must be aware of the privilege of being born in such a advanced society – and I say that, because information about anything and everything is one click away, the only thing that you require, is the will or thirst of knowledge. There is so much beauty in this world that we live in, the natural world being at the peak of it all, different arts that astonish us since their early beginnings – beauty is everywhere, you just need to take a moment and observe it.

Knowing that the world is so diverse and beautiful, I am inclined to believe that one of the best quests that man can set upon is to travel. Why cling to one tradition or custom when you can see them all, in every part of the world, why see yourself as being related to only one community or country, and not to the whole world – why not perceive yourself as a global citizen? So, while I do understand that tradition and customs were very important to some communities, in the century that we now live in, where everything becomes *global*, I think we should become more of a global community, and not keep certain customs that differentiate us.

What worries me, is the fact that, in the year that we live in, with all this technology and advances in science, with so much knowledge just there for the taking, I feel that some individuals around the world simply do not comprehend the opportunities that they have. How is it that so many profound people, like Sun Tzu, Lao Zi, Confucius, Aristotle and so on, were writing incredible philosophical papers, two thousand plus years ago, yet not many people even read or comprehend their work. It would be only rational that in this modern age, humans should have evolved philosophically as well, so that they could understand that everything in this world exists in relation to another, yet we are more divided than ever.

What worries me is that people still do not make the distinction between religion and faith, and that these exact things that teach us to be kind to each other and not harm others, are the exact things that sometimes divide us.

When thinking about the one aspect that I cherish in this world, without any doubt, it is human creativity. It is amazing what we as humans can accomplish when we get creative – particularly in domains such as arts, where throughout the years composers have left us breathless with their incredible creations, or painters and other artists amazed us with their works. There is simply no limit that we cannot surpass when we get creative – that is indeed one of the beautiful things in this life.

The world, as it is, it's pretty amazing, however, I do believe that it can be better. What I think we lack, and most definitely should come soon, is a humanist movement or *trend*. It seems that we forgot how to be human amongst humans. We let so many things divide us like religion, political views, the color of our skin, or different countries that we are citizens of, when, in reality, the only thing that should matter is that we are humans living on the same planet. So this is the solution that I would suggest to anyone and everyone, it doesn't matter that they may be in a position of authority or not, the philosophical path that we should walk upon is this one – we need to remember how to be human to each other. In my opinion, this should be the *philosophical movement of the XXI century*.

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